
FEATURES OF LINGUODIDACTICS IN INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE LEARNING PROCESS FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses some features of linguodidactics in improving the efficiency of the process of teaching a foreign language. A brief analysis of the concept of linguodidactics is given, defines a general theory of language teaching that studies the overall patterns of language teaching, the specifics of the content, methods, means of teaching a particular language, depending on the didactic goals, objectives and nature of the material are being studied. It is aimed at modifying objective patterns, according to which a model of teaching foreign languages should be built.

Keywords: *foreign language, speech, linguodidactics, teaching aids, teaching methods, competence.*

The complexity and dynamism of the development of the sphere of education of foreign languages in universities impose new requirements on its participants, primarily the teachers. According to these requirements, they need to have the appropriate knowledge, skills and abilities to organize and improve the educational process based on traditional and modern interactive methods of teaching foreign languages. To improve the efficiency of the process of teaching a foreign language, attention should be paid to ensuring the necessary level of speech culture of the teacher, the ability to use modern interactive methods and technologies, as well as the formation of reflective skills of students in the process of solving didactic and methodological problems. It is necessary to find the right solution to the emerging problem situations when teaching foreign languages.

Language, speech and speech activity are the main aspects of linguistic phenomena. The main types of speech activity were identified by L. V. Shcherba, who, however, believed that speech activity is one of the aspects of the language. He proposed to distinguish three aspects of language: speech, i.e., the process of

speaking and understanding; language, i.e., ordered linguistic experience; linguistic material, i.e., disordered linguistic experience.

The category of being (forms of being), or the “real life process” of people, covering both objectively given conditions and the prerequisites for the activities of individuals and generations, is taken in linguodidactics as the central category underlying the allocation of communication spheres as sociocommunicative speech formations. This category "... allows you to bring into unity, integrate, theoretically summarize and comprehend through consciousness and language existential relations, which are ... a system-forming factor in the allocation of spheres of communication" [1]. This gives grounds to single out four macrospheres of communication, which are the initial factor for determining the areas of practical use of the language. In turn, these spheres correlate with certain types of speech, namely: 1) the sphere of production (material and practical) human activity - special speech; 2) the sphere of domestic relations - colloquial (everyday) speech; 3) the sphere of cultural communication, which is based on the processes of artistic and scientific creativity - artistic and scientific speech; 4) the sphere of socio-political (social) activity (the existence of an individual in society and in history, as well as the existence of society) - journalistic speech in a broad interpretation, including the speech of various mass media.

Therefore, the spheres of communication, i.e. the spheres of practical use of the language, in which the corresponding types of speech are realized, exist within a particular linguo-society. Each sphere of communication is inseparable from the conditions in which this communication takes place, namely: from the situation in the broadest sense of the word and from the specific extralinguistic context. According to M.N. Vyatyutnev, the extralinguistic context, or the context of communication, answers the questions of why and how a speech act is performed. This conditions includes the contexts of communication situations that determine who, where and when generates and perceives a speech statement [2].

Within the context of the situation, the final formation of the meaning, meaning and significance of the communicative act takes place, and the communicative situation itself is, on the one hand, a kind of incentive for verbal communication, and outside of it the latter is in principle impossible. On the other hand, the situation is a full-fledged component of communication. At the same time, many elements of verbal communication do not have their own verbal expression, since they are given in a situation and suggest the subject content of the statement.

Linguodidactics, according to Minyar-Beloruhev R.K. [3], is an independent science, including theoretical and practical methods of teaching foreign languages. For the first time the term "linguodidactics" was introduced into the scientific literature in 1969 by Academician N.M. Shansky [4]. And in 1975 it was already recognized as an international one. The Pedagogical Encyclopedic Dictionary defines linguodidactics as a general theory of language teaching that studies the general patterns of language teaching, the specifics of the content, methods, means of teaching a particular language, depending on the didactic goals, objectives and nature of the material being studied, the conditions of monolingualism, the stage of learning and intellectual speech development of students [5].

If linguodidactics, according to the scientist I.I. Khaleeva, is such a branch of pedagogical science that substantiates the content components of education, training, learning in their inseparable connection with the nature of language and the nature of communication, then professional linguodidactics is such a branch of linguodidactics that substantiates the content of teaching foreign languages to specialists. The main task of linguodidactics is to develop a methodology for teaching a foreign language.

The definition given by I.I. Khaleeva, who believes that linguodidactics acts as a methodological aspect of the theory of teaching a foreign language in relation to various desired results of this process. Linguodidactics makes it possible to identify objective patterns according to which a model of teaching foreign languages should be built, in the center of which is a linguistic personality. Following I.I. Khaleeva, N.D. Galskova [6,7] believes that linguodidactics as a science is designed to comprehend and describe the linguocognitive structure of a linguistic personality, to substantiate the conditions and patterns of its development, as well as the specifics of both the object of assimilation - teaching, and the interaction of all subjects of this process.

On the other hand, in science, the point of view is put forward that linguodidactics is a general theory of language acquisition and proficiency in learning conditions. From this point of view, this science is a theory of "acquisition" of a language or a kind of linguistic anthropology, acting as a "metatheory" for the development of a mode of production of methods for teaching foreign languages [8]. In a certain sense, this understanding of linguodidactics as a science is close to certain aspects of applied linguistics that are being developed in English-speaking countries.

G.I. Bogin rightly notes that linguodidactics explores the laws of mastering any language, regardless of whether it acts as the first or second. He was one of the first

to attempt to build a linguodidactic model of a linguistic personality, which, according to the author, is the central category of linguodidactics as a science.

It should be noted that foreign scientists traditionally pay great attention to language in substantiating linguodidactics as a science. So, for example, N. M. Shansky defines the monolingual and bilingual description of the language for educational purposes as the main goal of this scientific branch. Monolingual description includes: 1) analysis for educational purposes of each level of the language and its fragments; 2) linguistic operations to determine the content and structure of the corresponding section in the school course of the Russian language; 3) language blanks for a textbook, teaching aids and dictionaries; 4) definition and description for educational purposes of a minimum of theoretical information for study.

The bilingual description of the language for educational purposes is aimed at analyzing the similarities and differences of languages at various levels and determining the role of the language in the conditions of various bilingualism.

Recognizing the importance of conducting linguodidactic research in the above areas, one cannot fail to note the fallacy of linking linguodidactics exclusively with linguistics. Despite the fact that it is linguistics that is the essential factor that makes up the specifics of the methodology of teaching foreign languages, one cannot discount the multifunctionality and multidimensionality of the process of teaching a subject. The interdisciplinary linguodidactic approach to the analysis of the above problems is based on the data of the philosophy of language, linguistics, psychology, the theory of intercultural communication, the theory of mastering a second (non-native) language, psycholinguistics, etc. At the same time, linguodidactics is not a substantiation of one or another particular language technique. Being one of the branches of methodological science, "... which substantiates the content components of education, training, learning in their inextricable connection with the nature of language and the nature of communication as a social phenomenon that determines the activity essence of speech works, which are based on the mechanisms of social interaction of individuals" [1], linguodidactics acts as a methodological aspect of learning theory. This means that this science is called upon to develop the foundations of the methodology of teaching foreign languages in relation to the various desired results of current process.

The study of the characteristics of learning and language acquisition in the context of multilingualism, individual and cultural characteristics of students, their

age specifics, factors that determine the completeness or incompleteness of language proficiency, etc., is of great promise. Therefore, the relevance of linguodidactic research is due to the need to create an objective scientific basis for evaluating the effectiveness of teaching methods. and their further development, methods, which are based primarily on the idea of the formation of a linguistic personality.

As studies in the field of linguodidactics show, the level of language proficiency should be understood as a certain degree of development of the individual's communicative ability in terms of the effectiveness of the process of intercultural interaction with foreign backgrounds, i.e. with representatives of a different linguistic society. Foreign scientists A.A. Leontiev, I.L. Bim, T.V. Markova and others attempts have been made to describe the levels of proficiency in non-native languages, but in general they can hardly be considered successful. We can only talk about the standards of secondary and higher language education. Unfortunately, these descriptions are on different planes and often testify not to the level of language proficiency, but only to the level of language education.

Compared with others, in foreign countries linguodidactics and methods of teaching foreign languages, it is proved that existential competence, or rather, its components - individual psychological characteristics of a person that favor the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities in the field of a foreign language and their use in practical speech activity, is actually the so-called language-speech abilities. It has been experimentally proved that the common components of language abilities are well-developed mechanical memory, a high level of development of thinking, the degree of development of speech skills formed on the basis of the native language. In the process of performing a certain type of speech activity, it is necessary to have sustained attention.

Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that linguodidactics explores the objective laws of constructing the process of mastering a language by a student in educational conditions and its main task is to develop a methodology for teaching a foreign language. It substantiates the content components of education, training and learning in their inseparable connection with the nature of the language.

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